

THE HISTORY AND ACTUAL CONDITION OF INDUSTRIAL HERITAGE IN ALBANIA: THE PROBLEMS AND OPPORTUNITY OF THE METALLURGICAL COMPLEX OF ELBASAN*

Assist. Prof. Dr. Frida Pashako

Architecture Department, Epoka University
Rr. Tiranë-Rinas, Km. 121039 Tirana, Albania
fpashako@epoka.edu.al

PhD. Candidate Boriana Vrusho (Golgota)

Architecture Department, Epoka University
Rr. Tiranë-Rinas, Km. 121039 Tirana, Albania
borianagolgota@gmail.com

Abstract

The history and evolution of the industrial heritage of Albania is strongly link with the historical, political and social events of the country. Since the second half of the 19th to the fall of the communist regime (1991) a lot of public investments in the industrial sector have been carried out, often those were part of the cooperation plans signed with Eastern European states (Yugoslavia, Cine and Russia). The expansion of the industrial sector, especially during the communist regime, brought economic and social progress, representing the only redemption of the country from backwardness and towards the building of a modern aspect.

Since 1991 Albania has initiated a process of modernization and deindustrialization of the sites built during the Communist era without a strategic plan aimed at economic conversion and then re-use of these areas, as during the transition process was difficult to defend the republic and regulate private interests.

The paper presents a study about one of the biggest and interesting industrial site in Albanian: the metallurgical complex of Elbasan. It is located in central part of Albania and was promoted from communist regime to build one of the most important industrial sites, although being one of the most ancient cities in country. Construction started since 1965 with the establishment of the steel rolling mill plant, in cooperation with Chinese Government. Further on, were put into use the cement fabric, coke plant, almetry, pig-iron, steel; and lastly the nickel-cobalt and ferro-chrome plants. The whole area of industrial plant occupies a large area of about

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half of the size (about 460 km²) of the local government territory (about 1200 km²). After the fall of communist regime, a considerable part of the industrial warehouses went out of function, broke down and left without any investment. Today and after the process of privatization (started since 1992) some part of the complex are reused for industrial purposes, other parts are totally abandoned and represent a risk for the decay and pollution.

Our intention is to evaluate the importance of the industrial heritage in one of the most important industrial city of Albania in order to promote and to sensitize the institutions and the populations about the importance of such areas not only historical but also social and economic. In fact about 12000 of peoples have worked and passed a considerable time of their life there in the only site of Elbasan.

The methodology used in the study is based on recording, analysing and providing strategies for regeneration and adaption of this huge abandoned industrial complex, in order to transform it from a problematic asset to an opportunity and catalyst for the city. Furthermore, this will help national and international community to recognize the values and potential of industrial assets in Albania for the regeneration and sustainable development of the urban context.

Lastly, by this paper we give a contribution in carry forward the scientific research of Albanian industrial heritage.

Keywords: industrial heritage, metallurgy, industrial site.

History and evolution of Albanian Industry

The history and evolution of the industry and the Albanian intrinsically linked to the historical, political and social of the entire nation. The first investments in the sector were made by the second half of the 19th to the fall of the communist regime (1991), they were almost always related to political alliances with foreign states.

In the 20s the first concessions were given, issued in favour of foreign companies (French, Austrian and Italian), which invested in mining and energy, creating settlements of Patos-Marinza, Selenica and Petrolia1.

The communist state was being formed just after the Second World War, creating immediately a closure to the Western powers and an opening towards the east. Consequently was started an initial alliance with Yugoslavia soon faded for fear of assimilation.

The period 1949-'61 was marked by the pact with the Soviet Union. The Russian geopolitical interests were conciliated with the need of progress of Albania. The relationship was based also in mutual trade exchange. The Soviet Union import from Albania mineral products (chromium and copper) but also agricultural products (tobacco, fruit and citrus fruits). On the other hand it exported to Albania capital goods such as equipment for the industry and especially wheat and agricultural fertilizers. Moreover Russia was offering loans with minimum interest rates that followed were condones at all.

The cooperation affect also the state planning and management of resources and investment, in fact in Albania as in Russia were adopted the five-year plans, although they started with a two-year plan (1949-'50) during which was realized the first railway in the country (Durrës - Peqin).

The 1st plan (1951-55): had as challenge the industrialization of an economy based almost on agriculture and to create scientific and technical skills of the workforce. Also it aimed to guarantee valuable technical - scientific support, which was offered thanks to the cooperation with the Soviet Union. In fact in those years a lot of Soviet specialists worked in Albania, transmitting their knowledge in factories.

The 2nd plan (1956-60): pointed to the collectivization of agriculture through the creation of new agricultural cooperatives, at the beginning one in every village, later were merged for an extension of four hectares. Farmers are often forced to join.

The 3rd plan (1961-65): was marked by the rupture with Russia in 1961, due to the declaration of Albania in favour of anti-revisionism together with China, so it was time for new alliance. In this period they were realized some establishments such as those planned for the leather and shoes in Gjirokastra and Korca, for wood in Tirana and Durrës and other small plants.

With the 4th plan (1966-70): were inaugurated many important works in continuation with Chinese alliance. Although the Chinese aid amounted to only 10% of investments Albanians, so very low compared with the Russian one. However in this historical moment the

1 Akademia e Shkencave te R.P.S (1976) *Historia e Shqiperise [Storia dell'Albania]*, 4, Tirana, , II, pp. 55-67.

country had reached maturity and preparation for the process industrialization and an important number of factory were inaugurated as the Fier fertilizer industry, the mining and refinery; Vau i Dejës hydroelectric plant; Laç factory of chemical preparations, Durres the rubber factory; Korca factory of high precision instruments and Berat textiles factory. Also started the great project for the Metallurgical Complex of Elbasan.

The 5th plan (1970-75): aimed exclusively at large metallurgical complex in Elbasan. In 1978 occurred a rupture also with China and began the period of isolation and autarky.

Plans 6th (1976-80), 7th (1981-85) and 8th (1986-90) during isolation period, invested on the chemical and food industries as well as on the construction sector turned mostly in defensive infrastructure (tunnels and bunkers)².

Despite the impressive industrial growth, the central planning compressed the economic freedom through the controlling the strategic sectors by public enterprises. The extreme self-sufficiency of the last years had worn down the economy and with it the patience of citizens (-40% of production between 1988 and 1992) and the consequent collapse of Communism (1991).

Photo 1: Propaganda posters: Chinese-Albanian partnership voluntary work on background the name of dictator.

As a result of the enthusiasm for defeating the regime, the country is facing uncontrollable economic variables and subject to new reactions. It follows the creation of a transitional economy (from the controlled to a free one) that still marks the country, where an informal economy takes root quickly. This is the moment in which begins the process of industrial disposal. In a climate of collective euphoria where the prospect and the future was represented by the finally friend West, factories and cooperatives were abandoned and robbed.

After the 1992 elections, won by the Democratic Party, it embarks on a policy of privatization of public property³ and state-owned enterprises. The phenomenon involves the

² Parangoni (2012) Arkeologjia Industriale. Nje vleresim i trashegimise industriale ne Shqiperi, p. 51-100.

³ All private companies were privatized and the quotas were divided between workers. An emblematic case is the privatization of various shops. The quotas and property was passed to the contracts without considering that they are often on private property or buildings belonging to private owner before the communist regime.

entire system of small industries to medium and small craft businesses. Even the agricultural cooperatives did not escape this reform that brought to bankruptcy and closure.

As result of such reforms, the Albanian economy seems to take off. The foreign press attributes Albania the highest growth of gross domestic product compared to other countries of the East (1993-'95 GDP growth average 9% a year, while inflation comes down from 85–7.8 %). Soon it will prove a simulated growth and injected development, supplied by foreign aid and remittances from emigrants. While the industrial production stagnated, exports are cancelled and imports consist of customer discretionary (automobiles, televisions, etc.).

Meanwhile, results latent the closure and decommissioning of industrial facilities. The phenomenon will reach a second peak in 1997, the year of economic and social collapse of the country. The creation of a bogus financial system based on pyramid schemes, with excessive rates and suitable money laundering, had sedated Albania for a few years. The collapse of this system has led to disarray (destruction of public and private property) with a fall in GDP of 8% and an increase of inflation to 50%.

Currently Albania has undergone an intensive regime of macro-economic restructuring under the supervision of the International Monetary Fund and World Bank.

The modern condition of industrial plants is forthcoming abandonment. The phenomenon of the scrap has progressively degraded industrial heritage as well as representing a social case. In fact there are 32000 individual and informal collectors in Albania of which 12520 are gypsy⁴, which have as their only source of income collection of recycled material (ferrous and not). The consequence of uncontrolled phenomenon of scrap at industrial sites has led to significant structural damage to buildings which are likely to collapse. In addition, many ancillary and service buildings, which were made entirely of metal, were totally dismantled. Of them it remains only the imprint and archival documentation.

The progressive loss and the continued damage of the abandoned industry leads to the necessity of knowing the industrialization process of Albania, as a first step for the development of this heritage and starting point for the promotion of policies and reuse.

"Steel of the party" - Metallurgical Complex of Elbasan.

Elbasan, is one of the most important cities of Albania. It is located in the center of the national territory and is an important crossroads, for national and international transport connection. It is situated 50 km from Tirana. It's strategic location was appreciated since antiquities, in fact it was an important station of the famous Roman Egnatia road, that connected Rome with Constantinopolis.

The city has an important history as commercial center since the Roman and through the Ottoman period. Based on this tradition, during the '20-'30 in Elbasan an significant craft production was developed and also the first industrialization steps were done with the installation of the industries of alcohol, tobaccos and cigarettes, oil and soap. After the Second World War

4 Data collected by Eper Center, IFC, BE, ARA, vd. Online: <http://www.riciklimi.al/>

the city had important progress in the economy and urban development. A lot of new industries was established as food and construction factories, and an important investment was done in the so called "black metallurgy", that transformed forever the character and economy of the city⁵.

The decision for the construction of the metallurgical complex of Elbasan was part of an important propaganda agenda. The communist government after the rupture with the USSR, needed to show and confirm the power of the new ally, the Republic of China. Therefore, inspired from the visit of Chinese leader Çu En Lai in 1964, during the Fifth Congress of the Party of Labor of Albania, the communist leader (Enver Hoxha) promote the erection of the metallurgical complex of Elbasan as the most important industrial complex throughout the country, part of the fourth 5-years plan (1966-1970)⁶. He stated that the giant of Albanian industry would change the fate of the country through a fast and prosperous economic growth, thanks to the financial and technical support of the Chinese friendship. So he affirmed that would represent for the Albanians the "second liberation" of country after that one of the Second World War⁷.

The "Metalurgjiku" was conceived in the Fourth Five-Year Plan (1966-1970) promoted through Chinese partnership and was completed during the period 1971-'79. Its construction is strongly related with the jubilee of the liberation of the country (1969). It was an important date for the Party and its propaganda that with international aid of the Republic of China invested in 30 very important projects. The great aim of the fourth and fifth plan was to bring the Metallurgic Complex to a capacity of process of 800 thousand tons of iron-nickel ore a year and production of 250 thousand tons of steel, sheet metal of various dimensions, water, oil, gas conduit tubes, iron-nickel and cast iron for the foundries. This huge complex will be not only self-sufficient but it will serve all the industry of the country⁸.

To cope with the huge production aforementioned were constructed 520 buildings, including plants, factories and an important transport network inside with railway, cable car and of course streets.

This huge industrial complex transformed the entire landscape of Elbasan city. It was located on the west of the center city, limited to the north by the national road that links with Tirana and Durres, to the south by the river Shkumbini and to the west by productive farmland typical of this plain.

For the realization of the complex were moved 2.5 million m³ of ground, were used 830 thousand m³ of concrete and 146 thousand m³ of metal precast elements, that shaped the Albanian giant of Metallurgy. The complex had an strong impact on the transformation of the landscape and skyline of the city, the 2 big furnaces were flanked by high cooling towers and even more high chimneys that have become symbols of the hated and loved the city.

5 Akademia e Shkencave (2009) Fjalor enciklopedik shqiptar. vol 2. p. 585-588.

6 Halili, Nj. (2012) Geopolitics of Albania after the relationships with China (1961-1978). Published in scientific magazine Global Challenge. p. 39.

7 Instituti i Studimeve Marksiste-Leniniste (1981) Historia e Partisë së Punës të Shqipërisë. p. 337-357.

8 Klosi (1969) 25 years of construction work in socialist Albania. p. 21-22.

Photo 3: Isuf Sulovari, "The giant of metallurgy", National Art Gallery of Tirana.

Photo 4: Actual condition of the Metallurgic complex (photo of authors).

Survey of the actual conditions of Metallurgical Complex in Elbasan.

Dealing with EU and local governmental policies to rebuild the abandoned industrial sites in Albania, it is necessary to evaluate properly the most important ones. This study aims to analyze in deep the Metallurgical Complex, once considered as the “engine” of the economic development of the Elbasan city. The paper should include the record of actual situation, analysis of the industrial site and proposals for strategies of regeneration and adaption of the complex. This study makes possible a clearer introduction to national and international level of the values and potentialities of Albanian industrial assets with the vision of future sustainable development of local industries.

As the Metallurgical Complex of Elbasan emerged with the intention of creating large centers of production, the site represents memorable social, historical and engineering values. The industrial complex was seen as the pride of Albanian and Chinese specialist which worked together to construct about 520 objects and ultimate industrial lines.

The communist regime persisted in the industrialization process to create as called “the socialist society” and fill the gaps of the past by adding industrial domestic production. The construction and operation of Metallurgical complex included the work of 12000 of people, under state directives for the promotion of working class in the industrialization process. The “movement 1+2”, which implied the commitment of one qualified worker undertakes to qualify two others with no economic profit, was one of the various stimulations of the party to promote hard and qualified work. The ideology represented in the construction and working time of the Metallurgical complex of Elbasan reflected the socialist attitude. The new socialist worker was considered hard worker, disciplined, high performance and decent citizen, showing no personal material interest. Albanians felt proud of producing for the first time local industrial elements with high standard, meeting the domestic production requirements.

Photo 5 Actual condition of the Metallurgic complex (photo of authors).

The 460 km² of industrial territory comprises an area of about 300.000 m² industrial buildings, about 20.000 m² canopies and 36 km rail track which is connected to national railway. The following maps illustrate the most important factories located in the Metallurgical Complex of Elbasan.

1. Mechanical Factory (since 1974).
2. Medium Foilation Factory (since 1966).
3. Fine Foilation Factory (since 1974).
4. Wire Factory.
5. Main Electrical Substation.
6. Steel lamination Factory (since 1965).
7. TEC (power plant).
8. Factory 12 (produced agglomerate and Ni concentrate).
9. Furnaces.
10. Coke Factory (since 1984).
11. Nickel-cobalt Factory (since 1981-1997).
12. Carbonaceous materials Factory (since 1976).
13. Refractory materials Factory (since 1981).
14. Ferro-chrome Factory (since 1988).
15. Sponge Factory.
16. Remount (part of Mechanical Factory).
17. Lime Factory.

A schematic view of factories utilization could give a better view of actual situation. The following are described main industrial factories in terms of functional use before '90 and nowadays.

Factories that changed their function after '90:

- Sponge Factory - operates since 1997 in one of the objects of metallurgical complex, by private company "Expansion".
- The electrical substation - is still in function supporting the city of Elbasan. Part of the objects of this site are privatized for production of granite, gas and SO₂ (Starflex Granitis Koll, ELBAGAZ, Budogas and Production SO₂).

Privatized Factories that did not change their function after '90:

- Medium Foilation Factory – privatized by Kürüm Holding Group Albania (Photo 7). The factories assure now the production of lime, steel, oxygen and scrap processing. Furthermore, in 2013 Kürüm International privatized four hydroelectric power plants in Albania with 400 kw/h capacity to meet the demands of production in the industrial site of Elbasan. In 2014 the company produced 303000 tons of re-bars and 443000 tons of billets⁹. The objects taken by the company seemed to be restored and the site were contoured by high concrete walls (Photo 7).

⁹ Kürüm Holding (2014) Annual Report. p.27.

- Ferro-Chrome Factory - was privatized by AlbChrome. It actually produces ferro-chrome (mixture of iron and chrome with some composition of carbon). The plant is compound of two furnaces, both in function, producing high-carbon Ferro-Chrome¹⁰. The actual production capacity of 33000 tons is totally exported in European and other industrial countries. The first one was rehabilitated and put on work in 2013 by BALFIN Group.
- Refractory materials Factory - was privatized from 1996 by “Refraktare Sh.A.” Company, producing bricks.
- Coke Plant selection and Metal Plant selection – under the decision of Council of Ministers Nr. 378, date 12.8.1999, these sites were described as the change of owner wright from public properties to private owner.
- Cement Factory – privatized by Seament Holding in 2001, named today as ECF (Elbasan Cement Factory). It is located in the ex-Lime Factory, using the carrier to produce limestone and cement. The decision was made by the Albanian Assembly with the proposal of the Council of Ministers, by the law nr 8805, date 17.5.2001.
- Mechanical Factory – was privatized in 1996 from 439 shareholder with the name of Mechanical Factory sh.a. Nowadays there are still produced mechanical equipment.

Abandoned factories:

- Remount Factory – the factories are out of function and seriously degraded (Photo 4, 5). The warehouses are constructed with red brick walls and metal truss cover. Most of objects are one – two floors with high height. From the photos can be seen their degraded condition, with ruined walls and bare structure of concrete beams and metal king truss roof. Windows of abandoned warehouse have shattered glass in all facades and in some cases there was left no more than the naked object’s structure.
- The Wire Factory - was also degraded and not in working conditions.
- Transport system of 36 km long rail track which was connected with the national railway is nowadays out of function. From the skyline of the photo we can see the furnaces and coke factories, mostly out of function. Minor local private businessmen have used some of the small objects as warehouses for depositing cement sacks, but clearly have not done any investment for the overall conditions.
- The Furnaces - located in the southern part of the site, are highly damaged and also out of function (Photo 6). Most of brick walls have been decayed and only concrete structural elements apparently are not damaged.

10 Information from online page of ALBCHROME. Found at <http://albchrome.al/ferro-chrome.html>

1:17061

Map 1 from: <http://geoportal.asig.gov.al/Map.aspx?lang=AL>

Map 2: Itinerary of field trip (elaboration of authors).

Photo 6, 7: Objects of Remount Factory (photo of authors).

Photo 8: Furnaces (photo of authors).

Photo 9: Medium Foliation Factory (photo of authors).

Through years, the Metallurgical complex of Elbasan comprised a serious industrial asset to be faced. National Governments have given the opportunity to regenerate the degraded sites by the process of privatization and usage for a long period of time. Due to the massive extension, the privatization have segmented the entire entity and leaving out of function the most deteriorated factories. The site have been in jurisdiction of Central Government and Ministry, hence the Municipality of Elbasan have had no competences in imposing local will for site changes. Future developments propose international investments, from various countries which have expressed their interest for the site (as Italian and Belgium companies). One of the most creative events ever organized in the Metallurgical Complex was “Informal Mind”. In 2014, about 22 artists presented their works inspired by the local space and the inhabitants. This activity, the first of its kind, opens the path of future transformation of the industrial complex in a new perspective, taking in consideration creative industries and laboratories.

On the other hand, constant denunciations from the media (televisions, print and online media) have exposed and highlighted the high level of contamination produced by the Metallurgical Complex from the working industries. Results from the research made the Ministry of Environment in 2014 on the pollution level in the industrial site, show the alarming pollution levels, which are several times more than the normative set by BE. An interesting study was

made in 2003, about the air, water, soil and plant and animal production quality¹¹. Data were collected by the industrial toxicology laboratory in Elbasan. One of the most important parameters to take into account is the Soot/SO₂, which in Elbasan is about 2-3; very high in comparison to European normative from which Soot/SO₂ ratio should be 1¹². It is interesting to see that, according to analysis done from the laboratory, the concentration of metallic elements in water is within allowed standards, as result of the closure of most of factories. As a result, chrome and nickel are the most concerning elements in site. Especially soils which contain nickel need immediate rehabilitation, also because it is considered carcinogen. Agricultural lands are mostly contaminated by heavy metals like Zn, Cr and Cd, with a radius of 5 km from the metallurgical complex. These metals have high presence of carbon and iron oxide¹³. This study also have analyzed inhabitants near the metallurgical area. Almost 2000 people unable to work because of industrial contamination through years; from which, in most cases, pneumatic disorders have been identified. Dust released directly in air containing iron-nickel are the most dangerous ones.

Proposals and Strategies for Territorial Reassessment.

Albania, having the status of Candidate County in EU, has to make noticeable steps and show progress in implementation of key reforms. Preservation and promotion of local cultural heritage is one of the most important worldwide directives. Elbasan, with other important Albanian cities as Tirana, Shkodra, Korça, Kuçova, Fier and Durres, could be part of international route ERIH (European Route of Industrial Heritage). Taking in consideration the major role of the Metallurgic Complex in the city of Elbasan an in country, the complex could be regenerated in some perspectives as sustainable territorial and urban development, creating eco-friendly facilities.

Different thesis could propose the reuse of the site for industrial purpose, promoting sustainable new production and continuation of ex-industrial working processes.

On the other hand; being inspired from the social memory as the complex epitomizes not only the work of local citizens, but also their everyday life and social identity created by the city itself; the site regeneration could introduce totally new functions. As the actual industrial area is considered highly polluted, it could be very interesting to transform the site in a green park, promoting ecological cleaning. Moreover, as the city of Elbasan is located 45 km from the capital city Tirana and 82 km from the Adriatic Sea, can offer decentralization of tourism from the seaside by promoting local agriculture production. Regulatory planning could provide better involvement of the industrial complex by transforming the industrial site in an agricultural one, as located only 5 km far from the city center.

11 Tola Y (2003) Normative of air, soil, water, plant and animal production quality in agro-ecosystem. p. 26.

12 Tola Y (2003) The impact of industrial pollution on the health of living beings in the area of Elbasan. p. 50.

13 Sallaku F, Sulce S, Kristo I, Shallari S (2003) Pollution analysis of the elements Cd, Cr, and Zn as well as their forms of pollution in the industrial zone of Elbasan. p. 66.

Elbasan is part of the most ancient cities of county, summarizing itself 100 historical and cultural sites, 80 natural monuments, a wide range of natural assets¹⁴. Hence, from the architectural point of view, introduction of creative industries could generate profit for local, national and international traders. Being located almost one hour far from Tirana, the complex could easily upload pressure from the capital city and attract creative tourists and artists. Inspiring from some of the most successful examples like Ruhr in Germany or Barcelona in Spain, the industrial complex could be the house of start-ups for new artists, cultural centers, art galleries, experimental centers etc. Hereby, industrial heritage of the city could be visited in a large scale and enjoyed by the public absorbing the spirit of the time in a modern perspective.

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Authors Biography

Frida Pashako has a Msc. degree in Architecture and Phd in Architectural Design for the Mediterranean Countries from Polytechnic University of Bari (Italy). Currently she is lecturer in Epoka University - Department of Architecture (Historical Environment and Conservation Theory and Studio). Pashako is Member of the Scientific Committee for the Restoration at the Institute of Monuments of Culture of Albania and President of Albanian Chapter of INTBAU. Her research activity has been mainly focused on: Architectural Heritage in Albania: from the Traditional Domestic Buildings to the Modern Architecture (1920-40) and the Communist Architecture as the Industrial Complex. She is tutor and advisor for Master Thesis at Epoka University and Polytechnic University of Bari.

Boriana Vrusho has a Msc. degree in Architecture from the Polytechnic University of Tirana, in 2010, and a MP degree in “Spatial Planning and GIS Applications” from POLIS University Tirana in collaboration with IHS ERASMUS Rotterdam, in 2013. Has worked as a full time lecturer at “Aleksander Moisiu” University Durrës since 2010, focusing in city spatial planning and architectural building projection. From 2014 and ongoing, she is attending PhD in Architecture at EPOKA University, focusing in Albanian industrial heritage.

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